

Quantum Features Emerging from Energy-Independent Shannon's Entropy in an Infinite Well Potential?

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In (1), it is suggested that a quantum bound state's Shannon entropy (only the spatial version, not momentum) should approach the classical result (or Bohr limit) for $n \rightarrow$ infinite, where n is the energy level. In (2), we suggested that the free particle quantum state $\exp(ipx)$ maps directly to a classical free particle with respect to p and E , while in a bound state, one has an entangled state of various $\exp(ipx)$. This entangled state does not map directly to a classical bound state and it is only a kind of average kinetic energy $-1/2m \int dx dW/dx/W$ (where W is the wavefunction) which exactly reproduces the classical bound kinetic energy.

In this note, we consider the situation of an infinite well potential and suggest a priori that there exists a quantum free particle state which maps directly to a classical one. The infinite well potential is then the closest situation to a classical bound picture because it has a seemingly quantum free particle bouncing back and forth inside. (In other words, whatever mathematical function is used to describe a quantum free particle in all of space, the same math form must be used in the box which has no potential because at least in this region the particle appears free. If a quantum free particle maps to a classical free one, then we argue that the entropy of the classical particle is $\int dx/L \ln(1/L)$, where L is a length because $P(x)dx=dx/L$. This result is the same for any energy and this key feature should apply in the quantum case, we argue, but $P(x)$ must be different due to the results of the two slit experiment.

We ask: What mathematical function would yield the same entropy and yet demonstrate in space different energy values? We try to show that a periodic function in nx/L satisfies this condition. Without using the notion of a wavefunction $W(x)$ or $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$, we find that a $P(nx/L)$ satisfies this condition and leads to discrete energy levels without one needing to know the exact mathematical form of the periodic function.

Quantum Free Particle Wavefunction and Classical Free Particle

We consider the case of a free particle which does not interact so as to simplify considerations. In classical mechanics, such a particle is described by a momentum p and energy $pp/2m$ (nonrelativistic kinetic energy). For simplicity, we assume motion in the x -direction. We assume that results of a two-slit experiment have been obtained suggesting that classical mechanics is not adequate to describe these results which occur at small distances.

We use this as a starting point and postulate that it is the free particle state which most closely matches a classical one. We also suggest that p and $E=pp/2m$ are also exact for a quantum free particle state, which is not yet determined, but that interactions occur in a nonclassical manner as in the two-slit results. These results suggest nonlocality in the interaction.

The issue we then consider is that of a bound state. Classically, the particle interacts in each $dx \rightarrow 0$ and accelerates, but this locality contradicts that of the two-slit experiment. We thus suggest that a quantum bound state does not map in a simple way to the classical bound state, but one should still be able to knock out a bound particle (breaking the bound state) and it

should have a well defined p and $pp/2m$. It is not clear, however, from which x it is obtained because of the interaction spatial width displayed in the two slit results. (In fact, in (2), we discuss the bound state as an entangled one based on the free particle quantum states.)

The Notion of Shannon's Entropy

A classical bound particle has a specific p and $pp/2m$ at each x at t . This is a well defined trajectory, but one may define a Shannon's entropy for it based on:

$$P(x)dx = Cdx/v(x) \quad ((1)) \quad \text{This is based on probability proportional to } dt(x).$$

For constant $v(x)$ one has: $P(x)dx = dx/L$

$$\text{This leads to: Shannon's } S = - \int_{(0,L)} dx/L \ln(1/L) \quad ((2))$$

This entropy does not change with energy which consider a striking feature.

A typical bound state, based on a $V(x)$, should have a different spatial entropy if quantum mechanics differs from classical physics, one might guess. We have argued, however, that a free quantum particle seems to be map most closely to a free particle. We suggest that quantum mechanically one does not have $P(x)dx = dx/L$ (this does not describe the two-slit experiment), but that one should still have a Shannon's entropy result which does not change with energy.

The issue then seems to be to formulate a quantum picture which yields the same Shannon's entropy independent of energy as the classical free particle one, even though the spatial physics of the two scenarios should not be the same because of the two-slit results. In classical physics, one has a free particle bouncing back and forth between two walls. In quantum mechanics, the notion of nonlocality of interactions means that a wall should not be considered a sharp barrier, it seems. Considering a sharp wall as an impenetrable barrier seems like an extreme limit. We suggest that it means an infinite potential at the wall.

For a classical particle, $P(x)dx = dx/L$, but one does not expect this result for the quantum case because of the two slit results and nonlocality of interaction. The question then becomes: How should $P(x)$ change so that Shannon's entropy remains the same? (We note that one does not even need the notion of a wavefunction $W(x)$ and $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ at this point.)

We suggest a different $P(x)$ for a quantum particle in the infinite well and suggest that due to the nonlocality of interactions displayed in the two slit experiment that:

$$P(x=0) = P(x=L) = 0 \quad ((3))$$

At first this might seem unusual, but it seems to be consistent with a nonlocal range of interaction if the particle can actually be at $x=0$ and $x=L$. One must then consider what function to use within $(0,L)$. $P(x)$ must somehow respect the notion of a free particle within $(0,L)$, but at the same time show a different x dependence than the classical constant value. At the same time, Shannon's entropy must remain the same for all energy values. Classically, one may have all possible energy values and at this point, one might assume the same in the quantum case.

To put this idea in context, we consider (1) which calculates Shannon entropies for an arbitrary potential (which does not lead to free particle like solutions inside) and argues that as energy increases one should approach the classical entropy. He calls the Bohr limit. If the quantum $P(x)$ must respect the notion of a free particle within the infinite potential well, but differ from a constant and one must deal with interaction nonlocality based on the two-slit experiment. It seems natural to propose a periodic function. It is not clear the exact shape of the function, but it should have identical units within $(0,L)$. This, together with ((3)), leads to an issue because it suggests that one can only have positive integer identical units. This countable set does not map to all energies possible in the classical case. In particular, it seems that one has a discrete set of energies as a consequence. For each discrete n , one must have the same Shannon's entropy. We examine if this is possible without knowing the shape of the units.

As a first step we assume:

$$\int_0^L P(x) dx = 1 \text{ so for } n \text{ identical units one has: } 1 = nC \int_0^{L/n} P_1(x) dx \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Here } P(x) = CP_1(x). \text{ Then: } 1 = Cn \int_0^1 P_1(y) dy \quad ((5))$$

Thus, C is independent of n and $P(x)/C$ is really a function of xn/L .

Shannon's entropy is then:

$$S = -n \int_0^{L/n} dx C P_1(xn/L) \ln(C P_1(xn/L)) \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{or } S = -n \int_0^1 dy CP_1(y) \ln(CP_1(y)) \text{ which is not a function of } n.$$

In other words, without using any notion of wavefunction $W(x)$ and $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$, one finds for this case discrete energy levels and a periodic function for $P(x)$ in the quantum case of an infinite well potential. Furthermore, we find that $P(x)$ is a periodic function in xn/L , where n is a positive integer.

We note that this is only a consideration of spatial entropy so we consider the full quantum infinite well potential case next.

Quantum Infinite Well-Potential

We consider the usual quantum infinite well potential treatment to see how it maps to the above ideas. Following (3), one has the notion of wavefunction $W(x)$ such that $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$. We note that in a full quantum treatment there exists a free particle wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ which exists for all x . Thus, for an infinite well potential one must somehow restrict the particle to lie in $(0,L)$ with no $P(x)$ outside these limits. Like for all bound states (for consistency, one uses an entangled state:

$$W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((7))$$

In the infinite well potential, one has a special case in which $\exp(ipx)$ s cancel outside of $(0,L)$ to yield a $W(x) = 0$ in these regions. Inside the well one has a linear combination of:

$$\exp(ipx) - \exp(-ipx) \quad (8)$$

This leads to a sinusoidal result in $(0,L)$. One has the periodic result of the above section for $P(x) = \sin(nx/L)\sin(nx/L)$ with nx/L , but the exact shape of the function is known. One again has discrete energy levels.

The analysis in this section is more accurate than in the above because one starts with the form $\exp(ipx)$ instead of simply seeking a $P(x)$ which somehow respects spatial invariance within the infinite well. Nevertheless, important basic features appear from the above simpler analysis which match the full quantum mechanical treatment.

The Question of Momentum Entropy

The exact treatment of an infinite potential well leads to $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ so one has $p(\text{ave})$ within the well region. This suggests a momentum based entropy which does not appear in the simpler analysis of the section preceding the previous. One may consider $a^*(p)a(p) = P(p)$ and create a momentum entropy using this value. In such a case, momentum entropy changes with energy as shown in (3). As a result, our arguments seeking a periodic quantum $P(x)$ in space, consider $p(\text{ave})$ as a sharp momentum value and are not the full picture. Nevertheless, important quantum mechanical features appear, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to apply the notion of a constant Shannon's entropy for any energy to a classical particle bouncing back and forth between walls. $P(x)dx = dx/L$ regardless of the energy. We suggest that one might introduce a quantum mechanical free particle $P(x)$ based on the results of a two slit experiment. This suggests that interactions are not local as the particle can interact with both slits. One still has, however, a sharp p and $pp/2m$. We note that nonlocal interactions suggest that one does not have sharp x points in the quantum picture. We thus suggest an infinite potential well to hold the particle and suggest that $P_{\text{quantum}}(x=0) = P_{\text{quantum}}(x=L) = 0$ to keep the particle from the wall where its interaction should spill beyond the wall. We then ask: What nonconstant $P(x)$ yields constant Shannon's entropy while still respecting the notion of spatial invariance within the well? We show that a periodic $P_{\text{quantum}}(nx/L)$ satisfies this criterion with no notion of a wavefunction $W(x)$, or $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$. One does not even need to know the exact functional form of the periodic piece. The periodicity is in nx/L and leads to discrete energies. This approach seems to yield some key results of quantum mechanics without even the notion of a wavefunction.

References

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